

TABLE I PHYSICAL PROPERTIES AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF 2-METHOXY-1-NAPHTHYL CHALCONEAS

R	Colour and Crystal form	M.P***°C		Halochromism with Conc. H ₂ SO ₄	Yield %	Time of reaction (hours)	%C		%H	
		Chalcone	2,4-DNP				Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
2-OH	brown globules	165	259	black	34	49	78.72	78.94	4.91	5.26
3-OH	dull yellow plates	203	—	brown	30	50	72.65	78.94	5.57	5.26
4-OH	light violet prisms	161	234	violet	32	50	78.83	78.94	5.69	5.26
2-Cl	yellow globules	142	—	blood-red	89	24	74.61	74.40	4.91	4.65
3-Cl	yellow needles	140	217	red	81	24	74.52	74.40	4.38	4.65
4-Cl	pale yellow needles	153	—	orange	87	26	74.28	74.40	4.41	4.65
2-Me*	orange clusters	142	231	dark-red	62	37	83.72	83.45	6.09	5.96
3-Me	lemon yellow plates	121	—	violet	59	30	83.68	83.45	5.61	5.96
4-Me*	yellow prisms	114	—	pink	65	38	83.18	83.45	5.75	5.96
2-OMe*	yellow needles	130	210	blood-red	59	41	79.53	79.25	5.38	5.66
3-OMe*	lemon yellow plates	107	247	cherry-red	51	42	79.87	79.25	5.93	5.66
4-OMe	yellow clusters	144	—	blood-red	63	42	79.13	79.25	5.32	5.66
2,3-O(CH ₃) ₂ *	yellow prisms	127	—	pink	60	28	75.31	75.86	6.15	5.74
2,4-(OMe) ₂	yellow needles	148	—	orange	63	28	76.18	75.86	5.46	5.74
3-OMe-4-OH	orange clusters	137	—	violet	51	27	75.56	75.23	5.93	5.67
3-OMe-4-OH-5-Br	dull yellow needles	119	238	red	67	42	61.24	60.87	4.68	4.34
4-NMe ₂ *	orange prisms	150	—	red	58	30	81.06	79.77	6.59	6.34

* crystallised from ethylacetate

** All melting points are uncorrected.

Experimental

Preparation of 2-methoxy-1-naphthyl chalcone analogue :

These chalcone analogues were prepared by adding, saturated solution of caustic potash in 10% aqueous ethyl alcohol, dropwise to an equimolar alcoholic mixture of 2-methoxy-1-acetonaphthone and required aryl aldehyde at room temperature. The deposited compound was purified by repeated crystallisations from ethyl alcohol (Table I).

2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazones derivatives were prepared by treating an ethanolic hydrochloric acid solution of chalcone with the reagent at 80° and purified by crystallisation from ethylacetate (Table I). All melting points are uncorrected.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Director, H.B.T.I., Kanpur for providing necessary facilities, Dr. D. K. Agarwal, G.S.V.M. Medical College, Kanpur for microbial assay and Dr. A. H. Siddiqui, I.I.T., Kanpur for microanalysis.

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Phytochemical Studies on *Saussurea sacra* Edgew

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Manuscript received 22 April 1974, accepted 14 August 1974

THE genus *Saussurea* is represented by well over nine species in Kashmir¹, and only few of these have so far been chemically analysed². *Saussurea sacra* Edgew, locally known as "Jogiraj or Jogipathsha" has been extensively used as a medicinal herb by sadhus and hakims³, for a number of chronic ailments like stomach ulcers, piles, bronchitis, cardiac disorders, nose bleeding, impotency etc. However a dig in its chemical composition has so far

been avoided, probably, because it occurs at high altitudes in difficult terrains. In Kashmir the plant species grows above 3,800 m altitude in the fields of Apharwat, Tous maidan, Konsarnag, Amarnath and Harmukh mountains. For the present study the plant material was procured from Harmukh (3,900 m) mountain through the help of local Gujars.

S. sacra is a herbaceous perennial, densely wooly, stem 15–20 cm long, hollow unbranched, covered by a rosette of leaves at the base, leaf sessile, pinnatifid, 5–8 cm long, black, smooth. Involucral heads exposed, globose, wooly upto 10 cm diameter, pinkish, achenes 2–3 mm, cylindrical, terrate, pappus plumose and hairy white. Distribution Kashmir (Sapru 489) & Sikkim.

Experimental

For alkaloid determination nearly 10 g dry matter of the plant (flowers and stem), was extracted with ethylacetate and later with CHCl_3 . The extract was made alkaline with NH_4OH (pH 9.0) and then neutralised with 2% H_2SO_4 , made alkaline and extracted with CHCl_3 , and dried overnight over anhydrous MgSO_4 . The concentrated solution was subjected to chromatography over silicagel. The elution was carried with C_6H_6 , $\text{C}_6\text{H}_6\text{-CHCl}_3$ (4 : 1), CHCl_3 and MeOH, and the solvent was recovered under vacuum. TLC on silicagel (0.1 mm thickness) coated plates was used for the determination of the purity of various components. The alkaloids were identified according to the recommended physical and chemical procedures as outlined by Gilmann⁴ & others³, and R_f value of each component was confirmed by comparison with the authentic sample.

Terpenoids were isolated from the mother liquor after isolating the alkaloids, with petroleum ether and the extract was checked for the neutral behaviour. The solvent was recovered in vacuum and the extract was subjected to chromatography over Al_2O_3 and Kieselguhr⁵ (4 : 1) in a solution of petroleum ether (b.p. 60°–80°) at a temperature of 12°–20°. The chromatogram, was eluted with petroleum ether, C_6H_6 , EtOAc, EtOH+ CHCl_3 (1 : 4) successively. On removing the solvents in vacuum, each fraction was subjected to TLC on silicagel and starch (19 : 1)⁷ to determine the homogeneity of the components. R_f values were compared with the authentic samples and confirmation of the components was done according to the methods as outlined by Guenther⁶. TLC spots were analysed under U.V. light.

Results

The alkaloid part gave two main fractions (i) Saussurol (7.0% by wt), m.p. 222°–224°, and (ii) Colchicine (2.0% by weight), m.p. 140°, $\alpha_D^{20} +116^\circ$, s' (C = 1 : 20 in CHCl_3) and (iii) $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{29}\text{O}_5\text{N}$ (0.6%) having $\alpha_D^{20} +108^\circ, 45'$, m.p. 125.7°–126.0°. TLC showed the presence of three more components with R_f values 0.45, 0.67 and 0.74. These components remain unidentified.

The terpenoids present within the aerial parts of the plant are l-cadinol (40.0%), limonene (3.0%), β -amyrenol (0.3%) and its acetate (0.6%). The percentage composition is based on the weight percent.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. P. Kachroo (Dept. of Botany) and Prof. R. P. Jerathi (Department of Applied Chemistry) for providing laboratory facilities.

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Potentiometric Investigations of Monobromo-Acetate and Monoiodoacetate Complexes of Cadmium (II)

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Manuscript received 6 August 1973; accepted 8 July 1974

THIS communication reports the investigations of monobromo-acetate and mono-iodo-acetate complexes of cadmium (II) by potentiometric method.

Experimental

Cadmium metal electrodes were prepared by the procedure suggested by Meites and Thomas¹ as in case of our investigations of Copper-Halo-carboxylate complexes². The potentiometric measurements were carried out by procedure similar to that adopted by Ferrel³. S.C.E. was employed as reference.

All the investigations were carried out at constant temperature 30°. Sodium salt solutions of the ligands were used. pH was maintained constant by keeping free acid salt ratio 1 : 20. The ligand concentration in the series of solutions of a system was kept significantly lower than the ionic strength which was adjusted by adding Potassium nitrate.

Results and Discussions

The composition and the overall formation constants " β_j " of the complexes were determined by Leden's⁴ method from the potentiometric data.

The calculated values of the overall formation constants are given in the following table.

Ligand	μ	TABLE		
		[L] Range	β_1	β_2
M.B.A.	0.75	0–0.5M	7.4	6.4
M.I.A.	0.75	0–0.5M	9.7	4.7

Formation of two complexes $[\text{CdX}]^+$ and $[\text{CdX}_2]^0$ (where X represents M.B.A. and M.I.A.) by monobromoacetic and monoiodo acetic acids at ionic strength 0.75 and ligand concentration 0–0.5M is indicated.